

THE USE OF ADVANCED PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FAIRY TALES GIVEN IN THE TEXTBOOK OF THE 4TH CLASS

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Abstract: In this article, the use of pedagogical technologies in primary school reading classes, the role of pedagogical technologies in improving students' knowledge, and methods of using pedagogical technologies in the course of the lesson are covered.

Key words: pedagogical technology, didactic games, study motives, free and independent ability.

Introduction: In Uzbekistan, with the honor of independence, fundamental reforms were implemented in all areas, the Uzbek model of economic development, the national program of personnel training was developed and is being implemented step by step. In our country, special attention is paid to the field of education, necessary conditions and opportunities are being created for educating the next generation. Today, we all know that the information communication system is developing at a high level on a global scale, and this, among other areas, has entered into the educational process and has an impact on its higher quality organization. In such conditions, it is natural that the theoretical and practical aspects of human activity are continuously updated. Pedagogical activity is no exception as a special and complex type of work. Educators are trying to achieve guaranteed results in their activities. Analysis of the result: the fact that the 21st century is recognized by our scientists as the age of information technology, pedagogical and information technologies are developing day by day in all fields, including the wide use of new information technologies in the field of education, leading to more effective and higher results than traditional teaching methods. is coming Provision of new information to the educational process on the basis of pedagogic and information technologies, computerization and computer networks is developing as envisaged in the "National Personnel Training Program".

Primary education undoubtedly lays a solid foundation in the development of a perfect human being. In the standard of primary education, the qualities of students' reading skills and ability to think creatively, to be able to control themselves, to master the culture of speech, and to master the skills of literate writing are specially noted.

In our country, paying special attention to the content of education, new versions of DTS educational programs are being experimentally tested, pedagogical technologies and information communication tools are used to increase the effectiveness of the educational process on the basis of pedagogical technologies. The subject of "reading" in the primary grade is to expand students' thinking activities, to be able to think freely, to understand the opinions of others, to be able to express their thoughts fluently in writing, to be able to freely communicate with members of society. serves skills and competencies. Tasks set for classroom reading lessons:

1. Improving reading skills. Qualities of the level of excellence in students: formation of correct, fast, conscious, expressive reading skills.
2. To instill in children a love for books, to teach them to use books, to get the necessary knowledge from them, that is, to cultivate deep-thinking, thoughtful readers who love books and know how to work with books.
3. Expanding and deepening students' knowledge about the environment, forming the elements of a scientific outlook.
4. Educating students in the spirit of love for work, morally and aesthetically.
5. Development of students' speech (mainly oral speech).
6. Formation of elements of literary imagination.

The content of reading lessons in primary grades:

1. The correct choice of educational methods and their appropriate use - helps to ensure the effectiveness of education. Because this period is characterized by the transition of the child from playing activities to intellectual activities, that is, to educational activities. The use of various games is of great importance in the development of a child's educational activity. Children perfect their knowledge through play and learn it deeply. From this point of view, the role of didactic games used in the educational process is incomparable. Didactic games increase the efficiency of the educational process, develop students' activity and study motivation in the educational process. Reading motives play an important role in organizing the educational process based on pedagogical technologies. Free and independent ability of elementary school students is formed in the process of reading lessons organized on the basis of pedagogical technologies.

As a result of the formation of the ability to think independently, students are able to understand the laws of the world and society, as well as human qualities through the positive and negative characters in the work, to study knowledge in depth, to think broadly, and to make appropriate decisions. Determining the content of education in the use of pedagogical technologies, preparing the forms and tools of education, developing a system of tasks aimed at wide acquisition of knowledge and mastery of spiritual qualities by students, the result of education and the level of mastery organizes such as preparation of test tasks for identification, objective evaluation. Effective organization of education of primary school students, content, forms and tools of pedagogical technologies, methods of correct and efficient use of pedagogical technologies in teaching, innovations in the field of education carried out to achieve a guaranteed result. 'learning, use in practice determines the practical importance of the work. Since the educational process is an extremely complex process, the effectiveness of education depends on the activity of the pedagogue and the student, the availability of educational tools, and the organizational, scientific, and methodical perfection of the educational process.

2. The use of pedagogical technology methods clearly defines the scope of teacher and student activity.
3. The teaching method means the joint activity of the teacher and students aimed at achieving the expected goal in the educational process. Teaching methods determine the activities of teachers and students in the educational process, how to organize and conduct the teaching process.

Teaching methods for both activities:

- a) arming students with knowledge, skills and abilities by the student;

b) includes the ways used in the activity of mastering the scientific knowledge, skills and abilities provided by the students.

Conclusion: It is important to correctly choose the methods, tools and forms of pedagogical technologies and use them in order to easily master primary school students. Many methods of pedagogic technologies are used in the organization of reading classes. The first periods of school after kindergarten occupy an important place in a child's life. Therefore, the period of primary education is the most responsible period in the educational process. At this time, together with the child's literacy, his worldview is formed, and his thinking skills develop. During this period, every activity aimed at developing the child's mind has a great impact on the composition and development of the child's mind. Therefore, in this period, first of all, it is necessary to pay attention to organizing the educational process in an interesting and effective way, creating a motive and developing it.

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